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Drivers in Ensuring Traffic Safety the Role of Legal Culture

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***Abstract:** The role and importance of drivers' legal culture in ensuring traffic safety is analyzed in the article. Ways to improve the legal culture of drivers are given. Factors affecting the improvement of the legal culture of drivers are analyzed.*

***Key words:** Driver, legal culture, legal awareness, highways, traffic, reliability, traffic, vehicle, administrative responsibility, intersection.*

Introduction: The increasing number of vehicles in large metropolises causes problems of various levels. Today, the occurrence of "traffic jams" on highway networks in the city of Tashkent is becoming a normal situation. At some intersections, vehicles lose a lot of time as they wait for 4-5 cycles of the traffic light and more. Many citizens suffer from the gases released from vehicles at intersections. The relations of road users during the movement are characterized by a certain system that is manifested as a product of their mutual social development.

Road users engage in regular interactions while driving on the roads. In some cases, State traffic safety officers also take part in such events. Unfortunately, such relations do not always bring positive results for road users. Many traffic violators do not correctly interpret the application of administrative sanctions for traffic violations by a traffic patrol officer. The reason for this is that they do not properly understand that if traffic rules are not strictly controlled, the probability of traffic accidents will increase. Especially today, this issue is becoming more urgent. Due to the increase in the number of vehicles on the roads, driving the cars is also becoming more complicated. Today, in the process of driving a car on highways, many difficult situations are encountered. To overcome such situations, a

lot of skill is required from the driver, but what happens if the driver lacks such skill? It is self-evident that there are accidents on the roads.

If such a situation is not eliminated in time by other traffic participants, it is inevitable that a traffic accident will occur. In order to further increase road safety, the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been amended, and responsibility for violating traffic rules has been strengthened. In addition, on April 10, 2013, a new version of the Law "On Road Safety" was adopted. These regulatory documents are aimed at increasing road safety and ensuring safe movement of road users. In addition, information and communication technologies are being widely introduced into the process of traffic control today. Now, the facts of violation of traffic rules are taken into account through special cameras and sent to the control center. There, this information is processed and a notice is sent to the violator's address with the amount of the fine to be paid for violating the traffic rule. If the fine is not paid within the specified period, interest will be added to it. There is no doubt that this will have a positive effect on the safety of vehicles on our roads.

It is worth noting that it is difficult to ensure safe movement on our roads by increasing administrative responsibility. The reason for this is that it is not possible to install surveillance cameras in all places of the highway, and the employees of the traffic patrol service do not have the opportunity to monitor all traffic processes at the same time. Therefore, in order to ensure a high level of road safety, it is necessary to increase the legal culture of each road traffic participant. For this, every participant of the traffic should feel that ensuring the safety of the traffic is directly related to him, feel that by violating the rules of the traffic, he poses a danger to other participants of the traffic, be aware of the process of traffic on the roads should be approached.

Conclusion: Comprehensive practical work should be carried out to increase the legal culture of road users. First of all, it is necessary to further increase the level of knowledge of the specialists responsible for this field. Today, even in training programs for specialists and drivers, serious attention is not paid to this issue. For this reason, in order to increase the legal culture of road users, it is necessary to increase their legal literacy first. For this, it is necessary to form the legal literacy of every participant of road traffic from a young age.

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